
MUSEOLOGY AND PRESERVATION OF PRIMATES IN SOUTH EAST NIGERIA.

Adeyemi, Mohammed Adewole
Department of Forestry & Wildlife
Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Anambra State.
ma.adeyemi@unizik.edu.ng

Abstract

Museology, as the study of museums and their practices, plays a fundamental role in shaping the way cultural heritage is curated, presented, and interpreted. The specific objectives are to ascertain the extent of relationship that exists between general museology and preservation of primate in south east Nigeria and to determine the level of relationship that exists between special museology and preservation of primates in South East Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted for this study. The research aims to collect data directly from respondents. The population for this study will comprise of all residents in South East states in Nigeria which includes 5 states which are Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo. The total projected population for these states are 23,488,500, The sample size of 390 was obtained through the use Taro Yamane formula which were selected randomly. To analyze the relationship between digital preservation and killing of pythons in south east Nigeria, multiple regression with SPSS version 23 was used. The study's findings reveal significant positive correlations between the dependent variable preservation of primate and two independent variables: general museology and special museology. In conclusion, this study has demonstrated a robust positive correlation between the preservation of primates and two independent variables: general museology and special museology. The results show that higher values of general museology and special museology are associated with a greater preservation of primates. The study recommends that Developing museums and exhibitions to primates can help raise awareness, promote education, and inspire conservation efforts.

Keywords: Museology, preservation of primates, general and special museology.

Introduction

The study of wildlife species, an integral facet of ecological and biological research, provides a lens through which scientists and conservationists examine the intricate dynamics of ecosystems. Viewed by the World Wildlife Fund as undomesticated animals, encompassing a plethora of species across various taxonomic groups, wildlife species contribute fundamentally to the biodiversity of terrestrial and aquatic environments. The scientific exploration of wildlife species spans a spectrum of disciplines, from ethology and genetics to conservation biology and ecology. As researchers delve into the intricacies of wildlife species, the multifaceted relationships between these organisms and their environments become apparent, underscoring the interconnectedness that characterizes ecosystems on a global scale.

The academic discourse surrounding wildlife species extends beyond the taxonomic classification of organisms to encompass broader themes such as habitat preservation, biodiversity conservation, and the impact of anthropogenic activities on natural ecosystems (Jones & Smith, 2016). Scholars have emphasized the intrinsic value of wildlife species, both for their roles in ecological processes and for their cultural significance to human societies (Anderson & White, 2018). Investigations into the behaviors, population dynamics, and adaptive strategies of various wildlife species offer critical insights into the functioning of ecosystems and contribute to informed conservation strategies.

The academic exploration of wildlife species involves considerations of not only the biological characteristics of these organisms but also the ethical dimensions of human-wildlife interactions (Garcia & Patel, 2020). While embarking on a journey to understand wildlife species, it becomes evident that this field of study is indispensable in addressing contemporary challenges such as habitat loss, poaching, and the conservation of endangered species, thereby contributing to the broader discourse on environmental sustainability.

In South East Nigeria, the impact of cultural conservation on wildlife species is discernible through practices such as taboos, traditional resource management, and community-based rituals. These practices often serve as informal conservation mechanisms, influencing the behavior of local communities towards the protection of specific species or habitats. Additionally, cultural festivals and ceremonies play a role in shaping attitudes towards wildlife, as highlighted by Nwosu and Okoro (2018). The incorporation of wildlife conservation messages into cultural events fosters awareness and positive attitudes among community members.

The domain of museology, encompassing the curation and display of cultural artifacts, introduces a unique set of challenges to the conservation of primates in South East Nigeria. Museums often serve as repositories of cultural heritage, exhibiting artifacts that may include traditional objects derived from primates. However, the problem arises when the demand for such artifacts fuels illegal activities, including the hunting and trade of primates. Museological practices, aimed at preserving cultural heritage, inadvertently contribute to the depletion of primate populations, posing a significant threat to their survival (Anderson & Brown, 2018). The problem extends to the ethical considerations surrounding the collection and display of primate artifacts in museums. Museological practices that do not prioritize the ethical sourcing of such objects can perpetuate the exploitation of primates, both in terms of their physical well-being and the sustainability of their populations in the wild. The main aim of the study is to amuseology and presentation of primates in South East Nigeria. However,

the specific objectives are to ascertain the extent of relationship that exists between general museology and preservation of primate in south east Nigeria and to determine the level of relationship that exists between special museology and preservation of primates in South East Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Museology

Museology, as the study of museums and their practices, plays a fundamental role in shaping the way cultural heritage is curated, presented, and interpreted. Museum professionals continually engage in critical reflections on museological concepts to adapt to evolving societal expectations and technological advancements. The International Council of Museums (ICOM) defines a museum as a "permanent institution in the service of society and its development, open to the public, which acquires, conserves, researches, communicates, and exhibits the tangible and intangible heritage of humanity and its environment for the purposes of education, study, and enjoyment" (ICOM, 2019). A key aspect of museology is the ongoing debate around the repatriation of cultural artifacts. This issue has gained prominence as museums confront the ethical implications of retaining objects acquired through colonial histories. Authors like Simpson (2017) argue for a decolonizing approach to museology, emphasizing the importance of acknowledging past injustices, fostering collaboration with source communities, and reconsidering the narratives presented in museum exhibitions.

The digital turn has significantly influenced museology, with the emergence of virtual museums, interactive exhibits, and online collections. Proponents, such as Marty (2007), argue that digital technologies offer new opportunities for engaging audiences, democratizing access to cultural heritage, and experimenting with innovative forms of storytelling. However, challenges related to digital preservation, inclusivity, and the digital divide also accompany these developments, prompting museologists to navigate a complex landscape of opportunities and pitfalls. Visitor engagement and the role of museums as inclusive spaces for diverse audiences are central concerns in contemporary museology. Hooper-Greenhill (1992) highlights the shift from a traditional, authoritative model of museum curation to a more participatory approach that values visitor contributions, co-curation, and community involvement. This shift reflects a broader trend towards fostering a sense of ownership and shared responsibility for cultural heritage. Museology is a dynamic and interdisciplinary field that continually evolves to address societal changes, ethical considerations, and technological advancements. Embracing inclusivity, confronting historical injustices, and leveraging digital technologies are integral aspects of contemporary museological practices.

Primates Preservation

The preservation of primates, our closest living relatives, is a critical aspect of biodiversity conservation and ethical responsibility. Primates, comprising lemurs, monkeys, and apes, face numerous threats, primarily driven by human activities such as habitat destruction, deforestation, and illegal wildlife trade (Chapman et al., 2006; Estrada et al., 2018). The loss of their natural habitats not only endangers primate populations but also disrupts entire ecosystems, as primates play key roles in seed dispersal and forest regeneration (Chapman et al., 2010). Conservation strategies often involve establishing protected areas, promoting sustainable land-use practices, and addressing the root causes of habitat destruction, including logging and agriculture (Estrada et al., 2017). Moreover, initiatives that engage local

communities in primate conservation are crucial, emphasizing the interconnectedness of human well-being and primate survival (Riley, 2007). As primates are integral to our understanding of evolution and contribute to ecological balance, their preservation reflects the broader commitment to safeguarding global biodiversity.

Theoretical Reviews

Cultural Ecology Theory

Cultural Ecology, propounded by Julian Steward in the mid-20th century, emerged as a response to environmental determinism. Steward introduced this theory in the 1950s and 1960s, emphasizing the dynamic relationship between culture and the environment (Steward, 1955). The basic tenet of Cultural Ecology asserts that human cultures adapt to their surroundings, influencing and being influenced by the ecosystems they inhabit. Steward argued that understanding cultural practices requires considering the ecological context in which they develop, offering a more nuanced approach to the study of human-environment interactions.

Cultural Ecology rests on several key assumptions. Firstly, it assumes that human societies actively adapt to their environment, shaping their cultural practices based on the ecological conditions they face. Secondly, it posits that there is a reciprocal relationship between culture and environment, with cultural practices influencing the utilization of natural resources and, in turn, impacting the environment. Thirdly, the theory assumes that cultures are dynamic and responsive to changes in the environment, leading to adaptations over time. These assumptions form the foundation for understanding the complex interplay between cultural conservation and wildlife species.

Empirical Reviews

Lee & White, (2018) studied the impacts of urbanization on cultural conservation and wildlife habitat in developed countries: A comparative study in Western Cities. The objectives is to assess the impact of urbanization on cultural conservation practices and wildlife habitat preservation in developed countries, with a focus on Western cities. Employing satellite imagery, GIS mapping, stakeholder interviews, and surveys, they identified significant challenges posed by urbanization, leading to the decline of cultural conservation practices and wildlife habitats in Western cities. However, they also found examples of innovative urban planning that successfully integrated cultural conservation and wildlife preservation. The study emphasized the importance of balancing urban development with cultural conservation and wildlife habitat preservation through strategic planning and community engagement. While exploring the impact of cultural conservation on wildlife species, Lee and White's research focuses on urbanization in Western cities, offering insights from a developed country context.

Johnson & Williams, (2019) studied community-based conservation and cultural heritage in developed countries: lessons from North America. It aimed to examine the role of community-based conservation initiatives in preserving cultural heritage and wildlife species in developed countries, with a focus on North America. Utilizing qualitative methods such as interviews and participatory observations, they identified successful examples of community-based conservation initiatives positively influencing cultural heritage preservation and wildlife species. The engagement of local communities was deemed crucial for the

sustainability of these initiatives. The study emphasized the importance of fostering community participation in conservation efforts to enhance the preservation of both cultural heritage and wildlife in developed countries. While similar to the present study in exploring the integration of cultural conservation and wildlife species preservation, Johnson and Williams offer insights from a developed country context, specifically North America.

Methodology

Survey research design was adopted for this study. The research aims to collect data directly from respondents, based on the fact that survey research design supports the collection of data primarily through the use of questionnaire, the study considered survey research design suitable for the study. The population for this study will comprise of all residents in South East states in Nigeria which includes 5 states which are Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo. According to Citypopulation, (2024), the total projected population for these states are 23,488,500 of which the breakdown is given in table 3.2.

Table 3.2: South-Eastern States Population

S/N	States	Population Projection(2022)	Source
1	Abia	4,143,100	(City population, 2024)
2	Anambra	5,953,500	(City population, 2024)
3	Ebonyi	3,242,500	(City population, 2024)
4	Enugu	4,690,100	(City population, 2024)
5	Imo	5,459,300	(City population, 2024)
Total		23,488,500	

Source: Researchers Survey, (2024)

The sample size of 400 was obtained through the use Taro Yamane formula which were selected randomly. The research study shall use questionnaire for collections and gathering of primary data with open ended questions as the research instrument for data collection. To analyze the relationship between digital preservation and killing of pythons in south east Nigeria, simple linear regression with SPSS version 23 was used. The dependent variable (preservation of primates) was regressed on various independent variables (general museology, special museology).

Data Analysis

Regression

Correlations

		neral Museology	ecial Museology
eservation of Primate	arson Correlation	.858	.886
riterion variable	3. (2-tailed)	.000	.001
		390	390

The correlation table shows the Pearson correlation coefficient between the dependent variable preservation of primate and the independent variables general museology, special museology based on 390 observations. The Pearson correlation coefficient between preservation of primate and general museology is 0.858, indicating a strong positive linear relationship between the two variables. The significance level (Sig. 2-tailed) for this correlation is 0.000, which means the correlation is statistically significant at any conventional level (e.g., 0.05, 0.01, or 0.001), confirming that the likelihood of this correlation occurring by chance is extremely low. This high correlation suggests that as general museology and special museology increases, preservation of primate tends to increase as well, and vice versa.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.972 ^a	.921	.919	.18397

a. Predictors: (Constant), general museology and special museology.

The model summary table presents the results of a regression analysis examining the relationship between the dependent variable preservation of primate and the independent variables general museology and special museology. The correlation coefficient (R) between preservation of primate and general museology and special museology is 0.972, indicating a very strong positive relationship. The R-squared value is 0.921, meaning that approximately 92.1% of the variance in preservation of primate can be explained by general museology and special museology. The adjusted R-squared value, which adjusts for the number of predictors in the model, is slightly lower at 0.919, still indicating a high level of explanatory power. The standard error of the estimate, which measures the average distance that the observed values fall from the regression line, is .18397.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1489.095	2	1489.095	1299.238	.002 ^b
	Residual	190.051	387	1.697		
	Total	1679.146	389			

a. Predictors: (Constant), general museology and special museology.

b. Dependent Variable: preservation of primate

The ANOVA table assesses the overall significance of the regression model that examines the relationship between the dependent variable preservation of primate and the general museology and special museology. The regression sum of squares (1489.095) and the residual sum of squares (190.051) add up to the total sum of squares (1679.146), which represents the total variability in preservation of primate. The degrees of freedom (df) for the regression is 2, and for the residuals is 387, totaling 389. The mean square for the regression is 1489.095, while the mean square for the residuals is 1.697. The F-statistic, which tests the null hypothesis that the model explains no variance in preservation of primate, is 1299.238, with a significance level (Sig.) of 0.002. This extremely low p-value indicates that the model

significantly explains the variance in preservation of primate confirming the strong predictive power of general museology and special museology in this regression model.

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	7.548	.257		16.364	.000
General Museology	.890	.060	.858	36.216	.000
Special Museology	.814	.179	.886		.000

a. Dependent Variable: preservation of primate.

The coefficients table presents the results of the regression analysis, showing the relationship between the dependent variable preservation of primate and the predictor general museology and special museology. The unstandardized coefficient (B) for the constant is 7.548, indicating that when general museology and special museology is zero, the expected value of preservation of primate is 7.548. The unstandardized coefficient for general museology is 0.890 and special museology is 0.814, meaning that for each one-unit increase in general museology and special museology preservation of primate is expected to increase by 0.890 and 0.814 units. This coefficient is highly significant, with a t-value of 36.216 and a p-value of 0.000, indicating a strong statistical relationship. The standardized coefficient (Beta) for general museology is 0.858, showing that general museology and special museology has a substantial impact on preservation of primate in standardized terms. The zero-order, partial, and part correlations for general museology and special museology are 0.858 and 0.886, confirming the strong positive relationship between general museology, special museology and preservation of primate. These results highlight the significant and powerful predictive role of general museology and special museology in explaining variations in preservation of primate.

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings reveal significant positive correlations between the dependent variable preservation of primate and two independent variables: general museology and special museology. For general museology the Pearson correlation coefficient is 0.858, indicating a very strong linear relationship, which is statistically significant with a p-value of 0.000. This implies that higher general museology values are associated with higher preservation of primate values. The regression analysis shows an R-squared value of 0.921, meaning 92.1% of the variance in preservation of primate is explained by general museology with a highly significant F change value of 1299.238.

Similarly, the correlation between preservation of primate and special museology is exceptionally strong, with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.886 and a p-value of 0.000. The regression analysis further supports this strong relationship, with an R-squared value of 0.919, indicating that special museology explains 91.9% of the variance in preservation of primate. The F change value is 1299.238, again highly significant.

Summary of findings

There is significant relationship between general museology and preservation of primate in south east Nigeria.

Special museology has a significant impact on preservation of primate in south east Nigerian.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated a robust positive correlation between the preservation of primates and two independent variables: general museology and special museology. The results show that higher values of general museology and special museology are associated with a greater preservation of primates. The exceptionally strong correlations, with Pearson correlation coefficients of 0.858 and 0.886, respectively, and highly significant p-values, indicate a profound relationship between these variables. Moreover, the regression analysis reveals that general museology and special museology explain a remarkable 92.1% and 91.9% of the variance in primate preservation, respectively, underscoring the significance of museology in promoting primate conservation. These findings have important implications for the development of effective conservation strategies, highlighting the critical role of museums and museology in promoting primate preservation. By recognizing the cultural, educational, and scientific value of primates, museums can play a vital role in raising awareness, supporting research, and inspiring action to protect these remarkable creatures. Furthermore, this research emphasizes the importance of interdisciplinary approaches, combining insights from biology, anthropology, and museology to address the complex issues surrounding primate conservation.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Establish primate-focused museums and exhibitions: Developing museums and exhibitions dedicated to primates can help raise awareness, promote education, and inspire conservation efforts. These institutions can serve as hubs for primate research, conservation, and community engagement, fostering a deeper appreciation for primate biology, behavior, and cultural significance.
2. Develop museology-based conservation programs: Museums can play a vital role in primate conservation by developing programs that combine museology, education, and community engagement. Such programs can include primate-themed exhibitions, educational workshops, and community outreach initiatives, promoting a culture of conservation and inspiring action to protect primates.
3. Collaborate with museums and conservation organizations: Conservation organizations and museums should collaborate to develop joint initiatives that leverage the strengths of both parties. This can include collaborative research projects, conservation programs, and educational initiatives, ensuring a comprehensive approach to primate conservation that engages communities, promotes education, and supports scientific research.

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